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The Reception of Pascal's Mathematical Work by Leibniz

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One of the great admirers of Blaise Pascal (1623 - 1662) was Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646 - 1716). We survey many contacts and engagements of Leibniz with the mathematical works of Pascal. They suggest that more may be found in the many pages of the Leibniz mathematical papers yet to be studied. During his student years, Leibniz apparently had not yet come into contact with Pascal's works. However, when he served as a legal counsellor at the electoral court in Mainz (1668 - 1672), he encountered some of Pascal's writings. In February 1671, he was informed by an acquaintance in Paris, the orientalist Louis Ferrand (1645 - 1699), that Pascal – and not Antoine Arnauld (1612 - 1694) – was the author of the anonymous polemic *Les provinciales* (1657), a critique of the moral doctrine of the Jesuits. He also learned that in the meantime thoughts on religion, the *Pensées* (1669), had been published from Pascal's legacy (LSB I, 1 N. 69)¹. Leibniz, who shared Pascal's interest in religious questions, immediately recommended this book warmly to several of his correspondents (LSB II, 1² N. 59, 61a, 61b).

Since he himself was working on the project of an *Instrumentum Panarithmicon, Lebendige Rechenbanck*², he immediately asked Pierre de Carcavy (~1600 - 1684), the royal librarian in Paris, about Pascal's calculating machine. He probably knew about it as it was mentioned in the preface of the book on the air pressure experiments, the *Traitez de l'équilibre des liqueurs et de la pesanteur* (1663). Leibniz received further information from Carcavy by letter (LSB II, 1² N. 65, 94)³. In spring 1672 Leibniz travelled to Paris, where Carcavy showed him the *Pascaline*, Pascal's adding machine. In the legacy of Leibniz in the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Library (GWLB) Hannover a sheet with his notes on this machine is preserved (LH 42, 5 Bl. 5 r^o).

The four-species machine developed later by Leibniz is based in its external appearance on Pascal's adding machine, but it's internal working is based on new developments such as the stepped drum⁴.

In Paris, Leibniz obtained another work published from Pascal's legacy, the *Traité du triangle arithmétique* (1665), whose content was closest to his own earlier studies in combinatorics. Leibniz returned to these topics in 1672, and Pascal's triangle providing a summation symbolism to write binomial coefficients in a concise form also inspired him to

Notes written by Leibniz when inspecting Pascal's calculating machine. GWLB LH 42 5 f. 5 r^o. Scan: GWLB © Public Domain Marked.

construct the *Harmonic Triangle*, which he used for his successful summations of infinite series by a difference method (LSB VII, 3 N. 30, 53).

Since the spring of 1673, another work by Pascal became important for Leibniz: The *Lettres de Dettonville* (1659) on infinitesimal mathematics, published in a small edition during Pascal's lifetime. He probably was not able to acquire the book, but borrowed a copy from Christiaan Huygens (1629 - 1695). To this circumstance we owe detailed excerpts from the book he studied intensively, especially the *Traité des sinus du quart de cercle* (LSB VII, 4 N. 10). As repeatedly reported by Leibniz, the study of this book led him to the introduction of the *characteristic triangle* consisting of the infinitesimal elements of abscissa, ordinate and tangent at a curve point. With it he could finally perform what we now call integral transformations and find the infinite circle series still in 1673 (LSB VII, 6 N. 1).

In June 1674, Leibniz was visited by Étienne Périer (1642 - 1680), Pascal's eldest nephew, who asked Leibniz to show him his calculating machine. A year later, in June 1675, Leibniz was able to borrow geometric manuscripts from the Périer family from Pascal's legacy, as can be seen from a receipt (LSB III, 1 N. 53). Leibniz also received material from Pascal's friends: he owed a fragment from the Intro-

¹ In the following, references to the Academy Edition of *Leibniz's Sämtliche Schriften und Briefe*, 1923ff, are given with the sigle LSB, series (Roman numeral), volume (Arabic numeral) and number of the text in the volume. The texts of the more recent volumes of the edition are freely accessible via the page <https://leibnizedition.de/>.

² The text of this manuscript is printed in: Ludolf v. Mackensen: *Die Vorgeschichte und die Entstehung der 4-Spezies-Rechenmaschine von Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz*, München 1968, p. 128–138.

³ Excerpts by Leibniz from this book have been preserved, which were probably written in Paris as late as 1672, mainly containing information about Pascal's various scientific achievements (LSB VIII, 1 N. 38).

⁴ Ariane Walsdorf, Klaus Badur, Erwin Stein, Franz Otto Kopp: *Das letzte Original: die Leibniz-Rechenmaschine der Gottfried-Wilhelm-Leibniz-Bibliothek*, Hannover 2014.

duction to the Treatise on Geometry to Gilles Filleau des Billettes (1634 - 1720). In it, the proposition that space is the object of pure geometry is expressed, a proposition that pointed the way for the modern development of geometry⁵. The confrontation with Pascal's thoughts was of great importance for Leibniz's further mathematical, scientific and philosophical research on the foundations of geometry and the physical concept of space⁶.

Leibniz also received oral information about Pascal from one of Pascal's closest friends, Artus Gouffier, the duke of Roannais (1627 - 1696), with whom he discussed problems of game theory. One of the problems is to determine the chance of winning for two players throwing a fixed number of dice, one bets a six will fall and the other bets none will fall. Starting from the form of the triangle prefixed to Pascal's *Traité du triangle arithmétique*, Leibniz solved the problem in January 1676⁷.

In the same month, Leibniz also dealt intensively with the so-called division problem, one of the classical problems of probability theory⁸. Antoine Gombaud, known as Chevalier de Méré (1607 - 1684), had presented this problem to Pascal more than two decades earlier. It deals with a game of chance played in several rounds and poses the task of dividing the stake paid before the start of the game according to the probability of winning if the game has to be abandoned after a few rounds but before the originally planned end. Pascal found a correct solution and presented it in one of the treatises compiled in the *Traité du triangle arithmétique*⁹. As mentioned, Leibniz had a copy of this work, and he did not overlook the fact that one of the treatises dealt with the problem of division. But in his hand copy there are neither marginal notes nor annotations or underlining in this treatise. In fact, Leibniz did not take note of Pascal's approach and solution at all, but persistently attempted to find a solution, which led him to deviating (and incorrect) results. Even when studying the papers lent to him by the Périer family from Pascal's legacy he did not come across Pascal's ideas on how to treat the problem. This changed only when, in 1679, Pascal's quarter-century-old letter containing his solution to the division problem was printed in Fermat's *Varia opera*¹⁰. Leibniz acquired a copy of this work as well, worked through it and now finally registered Pascal's treatment of the problem.

After returning the papers to the Périer family, Leibniz received a second delivery, probably in early January 1676, which contained Pascal's studies on the conic sections. He

returned them to Étienne Périer with a positive expert opinion for publication at the end of August 1676 (LSB III,1 N. 90), shortly before his departure from Paris in early October 1676. Unfortunately, there was no publication before these manuscripts were lost, so that the excerpts made by Leibniz and his friend Ehrenfried Walter von Tschirnhaus (1651 - 1708) in 1676 are now the most important sources for these writings (LSB VII,1 N. 26; VII, 7 N. 61-65, 72)¹¹.

Manuscript produced during a conversation between Leibniz and Tschirnhaus, with sketches and explanations mainly by Tschirnhaus and subsequent additions by Leibniz. GWLB LH 35 XV 1 f. 12^o. Scan: GWLB © Public Domain Marked.

Among the best-known results of Leibniz's and Tschirnhaus's work on Pascal's texts is the transmission of the *Hexagrammum mysticum*. At a meeting of the two, which also took place in January 1676, Tschirnhaus made a sketch that gives the content of a general version of Pascal's theorem: If one connects six points lying on a conic section so that they form a hexagon of whatever kind, and if one extends the six sides to straight lines, then the intersections of the three pairs of opposite straight lines again lie on a straight line. Tschirnhaus then sketched another example, which dealt with the special case in which one of the pairs of sides is parallel to the other. Leibniz added some more words and lines that helped him to make the rather cursorily executed sketches accessible, and he added his own consideration of the special case (LSB VII, 7 N. 61).

Some of the excerpts made by Leibniz and Tschirnhaus were published for the first time in 1892¹² and found their

⁵ Together with another fragment and marginal notes, this extract is intended for printing in volume VII, 8: *Pascalii fragmentum* (GWLB LH 35 XV 1 Bl. 2), *Extrait d'un fragment de Pascal* (GWLB LH 35 XV 1 Bl. 13), *Marginalien in Blaise Pascal, Traité Du Triangle Arithmétique* (GWLB Nm-A 605); see *Vorausedition zur Leibniz-Akademie-Ausgabe, Band VII, 8, Version 3*, DOI: 10.26015/adwdocs-2534, N. 33, p. 198–200; N. 34, p. 201–204; N. 40, p. 255–271.

⁶ Valérie Debuiche, *L' invention d'une géométrie pure au 17^e siècle : Pascal et son lecteur Leibniz*, in: *Studia Leibnitiana*, 48/1 (2016), p. 42–67.

⁷ See *De numero jactuum in tesseris*, in: *Vorausedition zur Leibniz-Akademie-Ausgabe, Band VII, 8, Version 3*, N. 10.

⁸ See the work known as *Sur le calcul des partis*, in: *ibid.*, N. 7.

⁹ See the essay III: *Usage du triangle arithmétique, pour déterminer les partis qu'on doit faire entre deux Joueurs qui jouent en plusieurs parties*, in: Blaise Pascal, *Traité du triangle arithmétique*, 1665.

¹⁰ See Pascal's letter to Fermat from July 29, 1654, printed in: Pierre de Fermat, *Varia opera*, 1679, p. 179–183 (with underlining by Leibniz in his personal copy, GWLB Hannover, call number Leibn. Marg. 176, p. 179).

¹¹ An attempt at reconstructing the treatise on conic sections has been made recently: Andrea Del Centina: *Pascal's 'mystic hexagram', and a conjectural restoration of his lost treatise on conic sections*, in: *Arch. Hist. Exact Sci.* 74 (2020), p. 469–521. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00407-020-00251-2>; see also Simon Dumas Primbault: *How Leibniz Read Pascal's Geometry. The Practice of Reading as Hybrid Hermeneutics in the Materiality of Leibniz's Pascaliana*, in: *Nuncius* 38 (2023), p. 103–136.

¹² Carl Immanuel Gerhardt: *Desargues und Pascal über die Kegelschnitte*, in: *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, Berlin 1892, p. 183–204.

Leibniz' annotation to the arithmetical triangle in his copy of B. Pascal's *Traité du triangle arithmétique*, GWLB Nm-A 605. Scan: GWLB © Public Domain Marked.

way into the editions of Pascal's works together with the other preserved notes¹³. The marginalia of Leibniz in the *Traité du triangle arithmétique*, on the other hand, were known only in excerpts until now and have been published only recently in the advance edition to volume 8 of the mathematical writings of Leibniz, mentioned above. Since numerous mathematical texts of Leibniz from the years 1672 to 1676 refer to Pascal, the origin of most marginal notes and underlined expressions can be dated reliably to the periods between spring 1672 and spring 1673 as well as end 1673 and middle 1674. An exception are the marginalia to the text *De numeris multiplicibus*. Leibniz had already dealt with this text in Paris (LSB VII, 2 N. 5), but these marginal notes were obviously written later, because Leibniz does not use the equals signs that he usually used in Paris, but rather the abbreviation *aequ.* for *aequalis* throughout. Furthermore, Leib-

¹³ The most important editions and translations of Pascal's works including the mathematical writings are: *Oeuvres*, ed. L. Brunschvicg [a. o.], 14 volumes, Paris 1904–1914; *Oeuvres complètes*, ed. J. Mesnard, 4 volumes, [Paris] 1964–1992; *Oeuvres complètes*, ed. M. Le Guern, 2 volumes, [Paris] 1998 and 2000; *Pascal im Kontext: sämtliche Werke auf CD-Rom*. Transl. U. Kunzmann, Berlin, 2nd enlarged edition, 2006; *Opere complete*, ed. M. V. Romeo, Milano 2020.

Today, large parts of the legacy of G. W. Leibniz belong to the collections of the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Bibliothek – Niedersächsische Landesbibliothek (GWLB) in Hannover, including his correspondence, which is listed in the *UNESCO Memory of the World* register, and his mathematical papers. Most of the archival material has been digitized and can be accessed online either directly in the library's *Digitale Sammlungen* ("Digital Collections") (<https://digitale-sammlungen.gwlb.de>) or via a IIIF interface.

With regard to the reception of Pascal by Leibniz, the following materials are of particular interest:

- in LH 35 XV 1 (available via <http://digitale-sammlungen.gwlb.de/resolve?id=00068203>): f. 1 r^o (= LSB VII, 7 n. 62); f. 2 (= *Vorausedition* VII, 8 v3 n. 33); f. 4–9 (= LSB VII, 7 n. 63); f. 10 r^o (= LSB VII, 7 n. 65); f. 10 v^o (= LSB VII, 7 n. 64); f. 11 (= LSB VII, 7 n. 72); f. 12 r^o (= LSB VII, 7 n. 61); f. 13 (= *Vorausedition* VII, 8 v3 n. 34); f. 18–23 (= LSB VII, 4 n. 10); f. 27 r^o (= LSB VII, 1 n. 26);
- in LH 42 5 (available via <http://digitale-sammlungen.gwlb.de/resolve?id=00051018>): f. 5 r^o;
- Nm-A 605 (available via <http://digitale-sammlungen.gwlb.de/resolve?PPN=1023099829>).

niz refers in a note to his own recent investigations on periods of decimal fractions. This probably refers to a number of texts from the first years he spent in Hannover, especially to the writing *De periodis fractionum decimalibus* (LH 35 III A 25 Bl. 1-3 u. 7-10), dated by him to January 1687, so that one can assume that the marginalia were written around the same time. It is striking that in the manuscripts mentioned there is no reference to Pascal, so the relation to his book results solely from the reference in the marginalia and the thematic context. This leads us to expect that in the many mathematical manuscripts of Leibniz, which have not yet been researched, further interesting connections to the work of Pascal could well be hidden.

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The Leibniz Archive: Research Center for the Leibniz Edition was founded in 1962 by the Niedersächsische Landesbibliothek in Hannover, today's Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Bibliothek – Niedersächsische Landesbibliothek (GWLB), as the third editorial center for the academy edition of the complete writings and letters of Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz. Since 1984 the scientific supervision is provided by the Göttingen Academy of Sciences and Humanities in Lower Saxony. The Leibniz Archive is responsible for three series of the edition:

Series I: General, political and historical correspondence

Series III: Mathematical, scientific and technical correspondence

Series VII: Mathematical writings

The remaining five series are edited at the research centers in Münster, Berlin and Potsdam.

With its editions and research, the Leibniz Archive con-

tributes to the accessibility of Leibniz's writings and the Leibniz correspondence, which has been granted the status of a *Memory of the World Heritage Documentary*. Researching Leibniz' life and activities, examining the content of his texts and developing the correspondence network are all part of the daily work on the edition: <https://www.gwlb.de/leibniz/leibniz-archiv>

The Leibniz Archive is further supported by the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Society, which is also based at the GWLB and publishes the scientific journal *Studia Leibnitiana* and organizes the International Leibniz Congress: <http://www.gottfried-wilhelm-leibniz-gesellschaft.de>

Together with the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Society, the four research centers maintain a joint portal with a wide range of research resources, including the newer volumes of the edition that are freely accessible in digital form (approx. 20,000 printed pages to date): <https://leibnizedition.de/>